

WP2: Standardization of eDNA bioinformatics pipelines

eDNA sequence to species

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O2.1: Optimization of reference databases, respectively gap identification and specification.

T2.1/D2.1: Establishment of reference databases

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Introduction

METAPLANTCODE provides standardized techniques and databases for the interpretation of metabarcoding data, tested in real and simulated environmental samples, with the goal of species level classification. Creating, facilitating and expediting harmonized biodiversity monitoring with the help of a curated, current, extensive, well-annotated, and user-friendly metabarcoding sequence database is a significant step forward in the metabarcoding aided biodiversity monitoring. This deliverable outlines the steps selected to build such a database, including the activities of searching for available data, collecting and filtering barcode sequences, and also curating the database. Lastly, a strategy for maintaining and making the database accessible is also provided.

Multilocus Metabarcoding

In plants there is not one universal barcode region, yet, DNA barcodes have shown significant success in plant molecular identification. Each barcode region can have its specific advantages and disadvantages. A barcode could perform better than others, in terms of amplification success and discrimination efficiency, depending on the specific condition of the sample, or the species present. Relative research suggests which species can be

successfully identified with each barcode region (Anthoos et al., 2021; Omelchenko et al., 2022; Taberlet et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2015). In environmental DNA samples (eDNA) it is important to have the best possible sequence coverage to be able to identify all expected species, but even sometimes the not expected ones, like in the case of invasive/alien species. In addition, the discrimination ability of each barcode region can also vary due to increased within-species variance, between-species gene flow (cross species hybridization), or even demographic separation. Multilocus metabarcoding can take advantage of the discrimination ability and specificity of multiple genetic loci, increasing significantly the biodiversity identification capacity. The selection of independent loci is also very important, in the sense that those loci are not in close genetic proximity and can be inherited independently from each other, offering additional information (Liu et al., 2017).

The analysis of eDNA samples includes several steps, like sampling, DNA purification, specific barcode-library construction, DNA sequencing, and finally the bioinformatic analysis. The bioinformatic analysis is the step giving a specific identity to each significant and uniquely represented sequence found in the sample. An important part of the bioinformatic analysis is the reference database used, which includes known barcode sequences, along their complete taxonomy, and other additional sampling metadata. Only the sequences with represented homologs in the reference database can be identified during the analysis, leaving non-represented sequences, unidentified. Thus, it is of great importance to use a current and extensive reference database for the analysis. There are multiple barcoding databases available today, each of them with their specific characteristics. The collection of data from multiple sources and the harmonization and curation of the data to facilitate eDNA plant metabarcoding, could secure the best possible species coverage during the species identification. Additionally, the publication of the database in a FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) way, the planning for regular updating and the offering of different versions allowing for filtering based on taxonomy, or licensing (non-commercial or commercial use), could benefit other metabarcoding eDNA future projects, while promoting open knowledge and innovation.

The molecular barcodes selected to be included in the database are the Internal Transcription Spacer, or ITS (including both ITS1, ITS2 regions), and the tRNA-Leu (UAA) intron, or trnL, especially the trnL-P6 loop (Figure 1). Those barcodes are genetically independent and represent both nuclear (ITS) and chloroplastic (trnL) DNA regions, while having significant success in plant molecular identification.

Figure 1. Barcoding genetic regions selected to be included in the MetaPlantCode barcoding sequence database.

Internal Transcription Spacer (ITS)

The Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) is part of the nuclear genetic region that includes the rDNA coding regions of the 18S, 25S, and 5.8S, composing the ribosomal rRNA core, in plants. The coding rRNAs include the 18S found in the small ribosomal subunit and the 5.8S and 25S found in the bid ribosomal subunit. The genetic region between the 18S and 25S rRNAs is known as ITS, which includes both ITS1 and ITS2 separated by the 5.8S genetic region (Figure 1A).

The ITS region typically ranges between 400-800 base pairs (bp), depending on the specific plant species and their genetic diversity, while it exhibits a high degree of variation even among closely related plant species. This high genetic variation is probably a result of a higher evolutionary rate of the introns found in the ITS, or the internal transcribed spacers ITS1 and ITS2, which are essentially non-coding. The high variability of ITS, along with the fact that it is flanked by highly conserved sequences, which allows for the design of universal-across species primers, makes it an ideal molecular barcode for identifying and classifying both fungal and plant species. Mostly, ITS has been utilized as a target for assessing fungal diversity in environmental samples, since it is considered as the industry standard marker for fungal DNA barcoding (Mahadani et al., 2022). Nevertheless, over 21,000 plant species have been identified thus far, utilizing the ITS barcode (Letsiou et al., 2024). Thus the ITS region has the potential to become a universal plant barcode, being highly universal and discriminatory. However, gene paralogues (multiple copies of ITS) and the presence of secondary structures can complicate amplification and sequencing, causing problems of application (Letsiou et al., 2024).

The existence of the highly conserved 5.8S loci within ITS, also allows for a more focused amplification of the ITS1 and ITS2 introns, which can also be used as additional barcodes with different plant specificity and level of classification discrimination. ITS1 typically ranges from 180 to 250 bp, while ITS2 usually falls between 200 to 300 bp.

tRNA-Leu (UAA) trnL intron

Plant phylogenetic studies frequently use chloroplast DNA barcodes, because chloroplasts are highly conserved, allowing for direct universal primer design, while their large copy number per cell facilitates amplification. Despite chloroplast's slow rate of molecular evolution, multiple regions rich in sequence variability have been used successfully as barcodes. The chloroplast trnL (UAA) gene, coding one of the leucine tRNAs (UAA), is one of the chloroplastic regions that have been of interest for metabarcoding studies. The trnL intron, found within the gene (Figure 1B) is especially useful in evolutionary studies between high taxonomic levels, since it is characterized by great variability. Plant species can differ greatly in the size of the trnL intron, which typically ranges from 250 to 800 bp, depending on the particular plant species and their genetic diversity. Furthermore, Gielly and Taberlet have described nine secondary structures, called loops, in the trnL intron (Gielly and Taberlet, 1994). Loop structures can be found in non-coding DNA areas and are frequently linked to hotspots for mutagenesis. Therefore, loops can result in genetic insertions and deletions (indels), or substitutions of nucleotides. The P6 loop in the trnL intron is a distinct area (shown in green in Figure 1B) that has been used as a secondary barcode, and can range in size from 10 to 150 bp (Taberlet et al., 2007).

Methodology

The methodology steps taken during the creation of the MetaPlantCode DataBase are presented in Figure 2, while other additional database specific information are analyzed below.

Figure 2. Visual representation of the analysis steps taken during the creation of the MetaplantCode DataBase.

Sequence Collection

Reliable ITS and trnL sequence datasets were identified from various local and public sources. Special care was given to the inclusion of significant metadata, along with the barcode sequences and the relevant license assigned to each of them. The following 10 dataset sources were used to build our initial database.

ARCTIC/EMBL

The Arctic and the EMBL datasets include trnL-P6 sequence data and metadata specific to plants. The datasets were created utilizing in-silico PCR and are available in Stoof-Leichsenring et al. (2021) under the CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0) Public Domain Dedication license (Stoof-Leichsenring et al., 2021). The dataset was accessed on 04/07/2024.

BOLD

The [BOLD Systems](#), or BOLD (RATNASINGHAM and HEBERT, 2007), is a very coherent database with internal quality control infrastructure. It includes multiple molecular barcodes, among which are also the trnL intron and the ITS as a single unit or as separate ITS1 and ITS2 barcodes. BOLD focuses the ITS sequence selection mostly around fungal identification, since it is considered the standard fungal barcode; however, other species are also covered. BOLD makes data available under Creative Commons, with each entry having its own license.

We have selected to utilize BOLD and not GenBank, since records from BOLD are submitted to GenBank upon publication, and sequences that are independently uploaded to GenBank are mined and periodically inserted into BOLD. This means that BOLD and GenBank are complementary databases, and as it has been shown, they can perform quite similarly during the identification of plants (Meiklejohn et al., 2019; Pentinsaari et al., 2020). BOLD was accessed on 10/05/2024.

CALeDNA

The California Environmental DNA (CALeDNA) program, started in 2017, is a community research project that uses environmental DNA (eDNA), or DNA from fur, mucus, spores, pollen, and other materials, to monitor California's biodiversity (Meyer et al., 2021, 2019). Among other barcodes, the ITS and trnL barcodes are also used and have become available. The CALeDNA project is available through the webpage [CALeDNA](#).

CERTH

Our local database of barcode sequence data for ITS2 and trnL was sourced. This database includes sequences from local Greek, mostly plant species from leaf, seed, and pollen samples. The database includes metadata related to the specific area of sampling, along with the taxonomy identification that corresponds to each sequence. This database has never been published in its totality before, and it was utilized to enrich the publicly available data with specific local data. The data will be available under the same license as the MetaPlantCode Database.

DAVIDLAB

This dataset (trnL-pipeline/reference/trnLGH.fasta) is part of the bpetrone/trnL-pipeline GitHub repository and includes the trnL-P6 marker, otherwise known as trnLGH. The repository has been developed by the David Lab at Duke University (Petrone et al., 2023) for the purpose of presenting pipelines specific for the DNA metabarcoding identification of plant remains in samples of human feces. Hence, the incorporated trnL-P6 reference database is focused on edible plants. The database is available here: [trnL metabarcoding protocols and bioinformatic pipeline](#), and it is available for use under the GNU General Public License v3.0. The database was accessed on 04/07/2024.

NATURALIS

Partners from the NATURALIS biodiversity center ([Naturalis Biodiversity Center](#)) have provided us with their local dataset of ITS2 barcode sequences. The dataset is available under the same license of all NATURALIS data (CC BY-NC 2.0 Deed).

PLANIITS

PLANIITS ([PLANIITS: a curated sequence reference dataset for plant ITS DNA metabarcoding](#)) is a curated ITS reference dataset that includes sequences from the ITS, ITS1 and ITS2 regions (Banchi et al., 2020). The database was accessed on 29/03/2024 and the data are licensed under a CC BY 4.0 Deed license.

PlantAligDB

PlantAligDB is an extensive online collection of nucleotide sequence alignments created for the use in plant research (Santos et al., 2019). The website ([PlantAligDB: A database of curated nucleotide sequence alignments for plants](#)) offers a comprehensive, regularly updated, and quality-checked alignments for use in evolutionary, phylogenetic, taxonomic, and molecular genetics research. The barcodes we used from this database were ITS, trnL-GH (includes only P6-loop) and the trnL-CD (Whole intron). The database was accessed on 04/07/2024.

UNITE

UNITE is an environment for managing sequences and databases that is focused on the entire ITS region as one unit. It includes eukaryotic nuclear sequences, which are clustered to the species level (distance between species in steps of 0.5%). The UNITE database is meant to serve as the standard database (Abarenkov et al., 2024), and it is licensed under CC BY 4.0 Deed. The datasets used were accessed through the site [UNITE](#) on the 24/04/2024.

Curation-Annotation

Workflow overview

A total of 10 databases were processed, consisting of 7 public databases and 3 in-house databases, as outlined in the Sequence Collection section. For each database, we focused on ITS1, ITS2, and trnL markers. Each marker consisted of a .fasta file containing the marker

sequences and a corresponding tab-delimited file (.tsv, .txt, etc.) with the related taxonomy information or any other available sequence metadata.

To streamline the curation process, initial R scripts and functions were developed for each database to retrieve the full taxonomy path (i.e., Kingdom, Phylum, Class, Order, Family, Genus, Species), filter out unnecessary sequences, and reformat or clean the retrieved metadata, such as geographical location and host information. To this end, the `{data.table}` and `{stringr}` package were used for data analysis, whereas the `{insect}` R package for processing taxonomy of the respective sequences. In particular, the `{get_lineage}` function was utilized to derive the full lineage of a taxon ID number from a given taxonomy database (for all databases the NCBI database was used.). It should be noted that while filtering was applied for retaining only plant related sequences, every information (sequences and taxonomy/metadata) is also retained for further process. Below we refer only to the analysis of plant related sequences.

The ITSx tool (Bengtsson-Palme et al., 2013) was then applied to the cleaned .fasta files to correct and extract the ITS1 and ITS2 subregions. Finally, the MetaCurator tool was used to construct a curated sequence reference dataset for ITS1, ITS2, ITS, and trnL markers from all the databases.

ARCTIC

The ARCTIC database initially included 2,289 sequences, all corresponding to trnL marker sequences. Using the `{get_lineage}` function, we retrieved the full taxonomic lineage for each sequence by providing the available taxonomic identifiers. We then filtered the sequences to retain only those belonging to the Viridiplantae kingdom. Since ITSx was not applicable to the ARCTIC database, the final dataset consisted of 1,894 sequences after the filtering process.

BOLD

The BOLD database provided a FASTA file containing sequences, along with corresponding taxonomy and metadata file (.tsv). It included sequences for several markers: ITS, ITS1, ITS2, trnL, and trnL-F. While all markers were curated and annotated, for this project, we will focus on ITS, ITS1, ITS2, and trnL:

- The ITS marker initially contained 241,442 sequences, which, after filtering for the Plantae kingdom, were reduced to 92,435 sequences.
- The ITS1 marker started with 6,013 sequences, and after filtering, 1,945 sequences corresponding to the Plantae kingdom remained.
- The ITS2 marker had an initial set of 125,203 sequences, which was filtered down to 116,358 sequences for Plantae.
- The trnL marker contained 608 sequences, all of which remained after filtering for the Plantae kingdom.

The ITSx tool was used for further curation of the ITS, ITS1, and ITS2 markers. To achieve this, all cleaned sequences from the previous steps were concatenated into a single FASTA file, comprising 210,738 sequences, which served as input for the ITSx tool. ITSx successfully detected and extracted:

- 87,183 fragments of the ITS1 marker,

- 123,253 fragments of the ITS2 marker, and
- 87,314 fragments of the 5.8S marker.

To reconstruct the complete ITS region, sequences presented in ITS1, 5.8S, and ITS2 regions were concatenated, forming the full ITS sequence. The final file consisted of 85,757 sequences.

CALEDNA

The CALEDNA database provided a FASTA file containing sequences, along with corresponding taxonomy file (.txt). The dataset included sequences for the ITS and trnL markers:

- The ITS marker initially contained 154,675 sequences, which were filtered to the phylum level, targeting Streptophyta, Chlorophyta, Bacillariophyta, and Rhodophyta. After filtering, 137,988 sequences remained.
- The trnL marker initially included 98,462 sequences. After applying the same phylum-level filtering, 98,460 sequences were retained.

EMBL

The EMBL database provided a FASTA file for the trnL marker, with taxonomy and metadata information embedded in the sequence headers. Initially, the file contained 17,623 sequences. Using the {get_lineage} function (from insect R package), we retrieved the full taxonomic lineage for each sequence based on the provided taxonomic identifiers. We then filtered the sequences to include only those belonging to the Viridiplantae kingdom. Since ITSx was not applicable to the ARCTIC database, the final dataset, after filtering, contained 14,854 sequences.

PLANIITS

The PLANiITS database provided three FASTA files for the ITS, ITS1, and ITS2 markers, along with the corresponding taxonomy and metadata file (.tsv):

- The ITS marker contained 104,342 sequences, all of which belonged to the Viridiplantae (or Plantae) kingdom, so no further filtering was required.
- The ITS1 marker included 104,846 sequences, all also belonging to the Viridiplantae or Plantae kingdom.
- The ITS2 marker comprised 101,584 sequences.

Although the PLANiITS database was already curated (as described in [PLANiITS: a curated sequence reference dataset for plant ITS DNA metabarcoding | Database | Oxford Academic](#)), we applied the same procedure for further curation using the ITSx tool. All cleaned sequences were combined into a single file and used as input for ITSx, which successfully detected and extracted:

- 104,348 fragments from the ITS1 subregion,
- 104,347 fragments from the ITS2 subregion, and
- 104,345 fragments from the 5.8S subregion.

To reconstruct the complete ITS region, sequences containing the ITS1, 5.8S, and ITS2 regions were concatenated, forming the full ITS sequence. The final concatenated file contained 104,341 sequences.

PlantAligDB

The PlantAligDB database included three FASTA files containing sequences for the ITS, trnL_CD, and trnL_GH markers, along with the corresponding taxonomy files:

- The ITS marker contained 9,885 sequences. We used the {get_taxID} function (from the {insect} R package) to retrieve the taxonomy identifiers based on the species names provided in the taxonomy files. Then, using the {get_lineage} function, we retrieved the full taxonomic lineage for each sequence. Since all sequences belonged to the Viridiplantae kingdom, no further filtering was necessary.
- Applying the same process to the trnL_CD marker, we retrieved 2,527 sequences.
- Similarly, for the trnL_GH marker, 34,674 sequences were retained.

The ITSx tool was used for further curation of the ITS markers:

- 8,973 fragments of the ITS1 subregion were extracted,
- 8,939 fragments of the ITS2 subregion were extracted, and
- 8,938 fragments of the 5.8S subregion.

To reconstruct the complete ITS region, sequences containing the ITS1, 5.8S, and ITS2 regions were concatenated, forming the full ITS sequence. The final concatenated file contained 8,938 sequences.

UNITE

UNITE database contained a large FASTA file. The file included 2,882,691 sequences with the relevant taxonomy information embedded into the sequences' headers. The [pyfaidx](#) tool was used to retrieve sequences corresponding only to kingdom Viridiplantae, while R curation was applied to create the relevant tab delimited file. The resulted file contained 423,900 sequences and was used as input to ITSx tool which extracted:

- 423,846 fragments of the ITS1 subregion,
- 423,716 fragments of the ITS2 subregion, and
- 423,704 fragments of the 5.8S subregion

Similarly, to reconstruct the complete ITS region, sequences containing the ITS1, 5.8S, and ITS2 regions were concatenated, forming the full ITS sequence. The final concatenated file contained 423,680 sequences.

In-house databases

CERTH

CERTH provided an XLSX file containing sequences of ITS2 and trnL markers:

- The ITS2 marker contained 495 sequences. We used the {get_taxID} function (from the {insect} R package) to retrieve the taxonomy identifiers based on the species names provided in the taxonomy files. Then, using the {get_lineage} function, we

retrieved the full taxonomic lineage for each sequence. By retaining only sequences corresponding to the Viridiplantae kingdom, 257 remained.

- Applying the same process to the trnL marker, we retrieved 48 sequences (from the initial 60 sequences).

The ITSx tool was used for further curation of the ITS2 marker sequences:

- 0 fragments of the ITS1 subregion were extracted,
- 250 fragments of the ITS2 subregion were extracted, and
- 0 fragments of the 5.8S subregion.

DAVIDLAB

The reference database of trnL sequences was downloaded (trnLGH.fasta). This fasta file includes the taxonomic assignment of the trnL-P6 sequences. More specifically, 791 trnL-P6 sequences from 468 different food plant species are included in the present dataset. As previously we used the {get_taxID} function (from the {insect} R package) to retrieve the taxonomy identifiers based on the species names provided in the taxonomy files. Then, using the {get_lineage} function, we retrieved the full taxonomic lineage for each sequence. By retaining only sequences corresponding to the Viridiplantae kingdom, 776 remained.

NATURALIS

NATURALIS provided a FASTA file containing 102,488 sequences of the ITS2 marker, along with a tab-delimited file containing the corresponding taxonomy information. All sequences corresponded to Streptophyta or Chlorophyta phylums and so no further filtering was applied.

The ITSx tool was used for further curation of the ITS2 marker sequences:

- 5 fragments of the ITS1 subregion were extracted,
- 101,378 fragments of the ITS2 subregion were extracted, and
- 2 fragments of the 5.8S subregion.

Further curation of reference sequence databases

To curate a comprehensive list of clean sequences along with their associated taxonomy and metadata, we utilized MetaCurator ([RTRichar/MetaCurator](#); Richardson et al., 2020). For this purpose, all sequences corresponding to the ITS1, ITS2, complete ITS region, and trnL markers were merged into unified files. By following the recommended pipeline, MetaCurator produced the final curated reference databases.

Availability and Maintenance Plan

The database has been made available under the name “MetaPlantCode DB” via Zenodo, to ensure a prompt public deposition of the data, under the license CC-BY or CC-BY-NC depending on the user's selection of the data they want to include. The present DOI for the

“MetaPlantCode DB” process and first steps is 10.5281/zenodo.18769845. Future iteration is expected to be created with DOIs (e.g. in case we have combined datasets), representing new releases of the same record, while ensuring the current and complete nature of our database. The frequency of the updates will be on a regular basis, and they will be published via Zenodo (preprint), and probably hosted on another dedicated website (Metaplantcode). It is highly important to allow access and aid usability of the created database, thus we have included such information in the database, allowing for license based filtering.

Future Steps and WP Connectivity

This deliverable ensures the continuation of other deliverables in WP2, while enabling the execution of other connected work packages (WP1, WP3), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Connectivity of WP2 Database construction (D2.1) to other work packages.

The “MetaPlantCode DB” enables the continuation with the bioinformatic analysis pipeline construction of WP2 and the analysis and further validation of the pipeline using simulated and real metabarcoding data provided through selected case studies from WP1. Best practices for the analysis of different types of samples will be provided, aiming for the acceleration and enhancement of biodiversity assessments for species, by building semi-automatic, harmonized yet flexible bioinformatic pipelines for metabarcoding analysis (WP2). Gap analysis will be performed using the “MetaPlantCode DB” in comparison to red-listed species and invasive species (WP2). In parallel, the database will be used in addition to other data for training the ML models (WP3). Harmonized annotations (WP5) of species names and other metadata will be further accomplished, while FAIR data publication will be ensured (WP4).

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